

A Case Study of Working from Home: A Common E-Business Model

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Abstract

The traditional higher education and training system has completely changed into online e-education via international institutions as a result of advancements in information communication and internet technologies. Students can enroll in these international institutions online and be able to work and study at the same time. We Propose The Concept Of An Online Office Model As A New System To Support The Online Education Model When Looking At The Online Education Model As The Next Wave In The Higher Education System. An online office backup system in businesses, the concept of "working from home," and other topics are covered in this article. Its advantages for customers, staff, and service providers. Such a model also lowers employee costs for travel, better home-cooked meals, and other expenses, while the service provider may lower costs for office space and maintenance. As a back-office system for a college-based education system, this online business office management system is used. This online office performs all marketing, admission, enrollment, management of online study material download, management of online attendance, management of online assignment evaluation, handling of student and faculty inquiries, support of examination-based evaluation, and monitoring of degree/diploma certificate generation functions. A group of online office managers working from their homes may manage and oversee all these online office tasks, allowing the It is possible to do away with the physical presence of online global education providers and colleges. Working from Home should have certain qualities in order to achieve its goals of offering all necessary services and resolving all stakeholder issues. Using the "ABCD Analysis Technique," the features of the "Working from Home" e-business model are examined. A model of various factors affecting organizational objectives, employer's point of view, employee's point of view, customers'/students' point of view, environmental/societal point of view, and system requirements are derived based on various factors that determine the working from home system using a qualitative data collection tool called the focus group method. The notion of working from home is being examined utilizing the ABCD Technique, a new Business Analysis Framework.

Keywords: *Working from a home model, online office management, ABCD Analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Working from home refers to persons who work from home or another place of their choice. then the working area by remuneration granted by the employer Working from home is quite convenient. In the last several years because the expansion of home networking means that employees can complete their tasks, on their own grounds Work will be completed remotely. It is determined by teleporting/telecommunicating. Agreements under which an employee is not required to be with their company during work hours In Working from home is becoming increasingly important in today's fast-paced society. to boost employee retention during We need some downtime in our hectic and stressful lives. Working from home allows you to have free access to a specific job through fewer interruptions from fellow employees in the office and communication time is also wider. With increasing numbers of employees working at home using the home as a working destination, it is clear that improved employee retention, e.g. home working can help retain working parents with childcare responsibilities. It

leads to increased staff motivation with less stress also. It also saves a huge expenditure towards installing a separate work office area and other facilities. A person involved in working from home can do his office work as well as home-required assignments simultaneously. Allowing employees to work from home to encourage a better work/life balance can lead to improvements in health and well-being. The system of working from home has some salient characteristics to fulfill its objectives and provide all the required services, thereby solving all problems of the stakeholders. The "Working from Home" system should have characteristics to fulfill its objectives to provide all the required services and solve all problems of the stakeholders. The characteristics of the "Working from Home" e-business model are analyzed using the 'ABCD Analysis Technique'. Based on various factors which decide the Working from Home system, a model of various factors affecting organizational objectives, employer's point of view, employee's point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. Working from home concept is being analyzed using a new Business Analysis Framework namely ABCD Technique.

WORKING FROM HOME MODEL

Modeling Working-From-Home Decisions the number of employees working from home has tripled Working from home has significant benefits for both the employer and the employee. According to the recent studies conducted even if the location of the study is different, the results achieved in terms of the output compared to the study during office hours are rather similar. There were no changes in productivity from the working group, but those who worked from home were 13 per cent more productive. The records kept by a survey agency showed much increase in productivity earned by the employees at home and they worked more hours than that of the work done in an office. The survey revealed that the home workers also reported substantially higher work satisfaction and less work exhaustion. To anchor our thinking before examining the data we map out a simple model of the impact of working from home on:

1. Firm profits,
2. Employee's hours, and
3. Selection effects. Firm Profits: We model the impact on profits of WFH as primarily

Driven by four effects:

- A. Hours: The number of hours worked from the official shift (as opposed to taken on breaks)
- B. Call rate: The number of (quality-adjusted) calls completed per hour
- C. Attrition: The impact on quit rates (which drive hiring and training costs)
- D. Capital: The impact on capital inputs, through office space and equipment requirements. More and more people are getting to work without going to work. Instead of commuting to a corporate workspace, they're staying at home in their own space. Instead of separating their work lives from their home lives, they're-blending them, or trying to. Instead of thinking of work as a place where they go, they're seeing it as something they do. While many relish the chance to strike a better work-life balance by working from home, some are surprisingly resistant to being stationed outside the office.

Methods of Working from Home

The person who wishes to work from home are individuals who need additional income or a parent who wishes to earn income and stay home with kids, this is the solution for them. There are various kinds of work, which can make at home.

1. Call centers: Selling the Time and Voice If you have an excellent telephone voice, an ability to organize information quickly and a quiet place in your home to work, you could make money working for a call centre, call centre means don't have someone to answer their phones 24 hours a day. The calls are routed to a call centre. And then sent out to individuals who work from their homes. These workers are equipped with computers and software are they can work on customers' questions.

1. Selling homemade products If people are having ideas of creating beautiful things at home, this helps them to supply the products while sitting at home. Homemade products are shown no signs of stopping— E.g. Gifts, Clothes, Vegetables (farmers) etc.

2. Consultancy Consultants offer their services or advice for free. Consultants are individuals, some people use consultants for tax or financial advice, while others may pay a consultant to teach them how to set up and maintain the work. If a consultant is proven their skills in an area, they can market themselves as a consultant and provide services from home.

Fig. 1 : Block diagram of issues affecting 'Working from Home' model.

ABCD ANALYSIS OF WORKING FROM HOME MODEL

The advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a business model can be used to analyze and understand the model effectively. As per this analysis technique, the effectiveness of a business model can be studied by identifying and analyzing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages by considering various issues like organizational objectives employers and employees' perspectives, customer/student perspectives and environmental social perspective as in the block diagram of issues affecting working from the home model shown in figure 1. The various factors contributing to the four identified constructs like advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely the focus group method and the constituent critical elements supporting these factors are identified. Factors affecting the working from home Model are (1) Factors related to organizational objectives, (2) Factors related to the Employer's perspective, (3) Factors related to the Employee's Perspective, (4) Factors related to Customers / Students service, and (5) Environmental / Social factors. Allowing staff to work at home on either a full or part-time basis can bring a range of business benefits - from increased productivity and greater staff motivation to more effective use of their premises. Home working also widens the base from which one can recruit, boosting their chances of recruiting successfully. The spread of home working is opening up a new range of possibilities for the way businesses can work and structure themselves.

Organisational Issues

Freeing Work from the constraints of location and time using Information technology supports new patterns of work, with greater flexibility in location and time. Working in a particular location - the office - over a particular period - the office day - is a key feature of the way industrial work has been organized for over two centuries. This mode of working has many obvious advantages: for individuals: 'it structures their time 'it gives them social contact, 'it gives them a sense of achievement, of the worth of identity. For the organization, 'it permits control and coordination of work 'it makes employees visible - hence they can be guided, evaluated, and developed 'it mandates the interaction necessary to secure consensus on organizational goals It represents a traditional, stable structure, to which the work can be accustomed. Most generally, there is a feeling that the way they traditionally have managed. Although it can bring great benefits, working with other organisations is more complex than working alone. The success rests on a combination of formal and informal ways of achieving good working relationships on both an

organisational and an individual level. It is essential to discuss how they will work together, defining roles, responsibilities and contractual or other legal obligations, and to get this in writing in a joint working agreement. People working in collaboration also cite the importance of values, such as trust, in their relationships. However, even where they have a pre-existing relationship and trust on which to build, preparation, planning and a written agreement can help them avoid misunderstandings. Staff and volunteers must understand why their organisation is working collaboratively and have an insight into partners' aims and values. Time spent developing an understanding of partners' cultures can help people from different organisations to work together.

Technological issues

Technology is being used in almost every company to accomplish specific tasks. Technology has changed the way people work and it has brought some fun to work, it reduces human errors which can be caused by too much work or stress. Business technologies like computers, tablets, social networks, virtual meeting software, accounting software, customer management applications, and so much more have removed workplace boundaries and they have also facilitated in the movement of information at the workplace which accelerates quick decision-making at any workplace.

Environmental issues

Depending on the processes they support, wireless solutions may have to handle sub-optimal conditions such as poor lighting, rough conditions, extreme temperatures and high rates of device theft and loss. Security is an acute concern for many wireless applications. Wireless data, travelling over open airwaves, is easily intercepted. Environment conditions are addressable through a full understanding of who will use the application and how and where it will be used. Security can be enhanced using a combination of techniques, from cryptography to authentication servers, to virtual private networks. Adverse work conditions can be addressed through the proper device and accessory selection, such as using earpieces for noisy locations and backlit displays for dim lighting conditions. The advantages and the benefits are overriding the constraints and disadvantages of various environmental and social issues in the case of working from home.

Employer/employee issues

Businesses perform best when there are strong working relationships between employers, employees and the business owners (e.g. shareholders). Decisions made as a result of a workforce plan inevitably both sides of the relationship – for example, A decision to make redundancies and reduce staff costs might be viewed positively by the shareholders, but negatively by the employees and trade unions. A plan to offer more flexible working options would be welcomed by employees but might place additional pressure on the workloads of line managers. The solution to these potential conflicts and issues is usually found through communication and consultation. Ultimately, decisions need to be taken in the best interests of the business – but it is important to at least attempt to gain the support of other stakeholders.

Customer's issues

At some point, everyone in business has to deal with an upset customer. The challenge is to handle the situation in a way that leaves the customer thinking you operate a great company. If you're lucky, you can even encourage him or her to serve as a passionate advocate for your brand. When it comes down to it, many customers don't even bother to complain. They simply leave and buy from your competitors. Research suggests that up to 80 percent of customers who leave were, in fact, "satisfied" with the original company. Customer satisfaction is not

enough. Businesses nowadays need to positively delight customers if they want to earn their loyalty. It may seem counter-intuitive, but a business owner's ability to effectively deal with customer complaints provides a great opportunity to turn dissatisfied customers into active promoters of the business.

Table 1: Advantages of Working from home model

Sl.No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Less Investment 2. Diverse People or Workforce 3. New pattern to work 4. Organisational worth	1. High return 2. Specialized Individuals 3. Readiness to Change 4. Revenue generation
2.	Operational Issues	1. Man power Utilisation 2. Cost effective 3. Less Time consuming 4. Flexible	1. Optimum utilization of resources 2. Less cost-higher return 3. Travel time reduced 4. Flexi time
3.	Technological Issues	1. High level of technology 2. High dependency on technology 3. Expand 4. Talent	1. Preparedness of Employees 2. Quick & Instant 3. Employee empowerment
4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Reduces staff cost 2. saving of office space 3. Balancing life & work 4. Flexible working option	1. Control mechanism 2. Increases earning 3. More productive 4. Manpower supply more

Table 2 : Benefits of Working from home model

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Financial stability 2. More productivity 3. Attracts & Retain staff 4. Employer brand	1. Less investment in terms of office space. 2. Working at your risk 3. More supply of manpower 4. Royal Employees
2.	Operational Issues	1. Improved quality 2. Operational efficiency 3. Networking 4. Speed	1. Quality of work 2. Increases 3. Maintenance cost is less 4. Quick result
3.	Technological Issues	1. Availability 2. Technical superior 3. Improves communication 4. Ability to handle	1. Cheap & affordable 2. Latest technology 3. Formal Vs. Informal 4. Easy & safer
4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Saves Employer Investment 2. Reduces unscheduled absence 3. Organisational structure 4. Mutuality	1. Equitable load 2. Better performance 3. Virtual 4. Interaction/ Networking

JOBS SUITED FOR WORK FROM HOME:

Due to several limitations associated with nature of the job, it is evident that not all work can be performed from home. In research as well as in practice there are not many studies to show how many fractions of the total workforce can perform their task by WFH arrangements. However, there has been some recent development in this direction and through newer research, we can do some predictive analysis. We have to be very careful that these data are from high-income countries and can't be

replicated in the Indian context in entirety where all the necessary infrastructures for WFH have recently started to evolve.

Table—1

Occupations Suitable for WFH

Jobs works From Home	No of Jobs	Covid Period Work Home
Manager	52	35
Academics	52	45
Technicians	43	25
Clerical	67	45
Sales & Services	29	19
Skilled Agriculture	0	0
Craft Workers	21	15
Plant machine	0	0
Elementary Occupation	0	0

Graph—1

Occupations Suitable for WFH

	WFH	WIO		
	Mean	Mean	Diff.	P-Value
Female	0.4066	0.5038	-0.0972	0.0000
Age	44.4219	43.7277	0.6942	0.0637
Partner	0.8844	0.8400	0.0444	0.0005
Children under 16 Years	0.3787	0.3203	0.0584	0.0018
Years of Schooling	14.6506	12.2214	2.4292	0.0000
Part-time Work	0.1690	0.2361	-0.0671	0.0000
Experience in Full-time Work	17.2165	17.1670	0.0495	0.9048
Experience in Part-time Work	2.6982	3.3161	-0.6179	0.0015
Tenure	11.9502	12.4079	-0.4577	0.2245
Leadership Position	0.6366	0.1492	0.4874	0.0000
Monthly Gross Wage	3942.7010	2472.8190	1469.8820	0.0000
Commuting Distance	33.1741	20.3271	12.8470	0.0000

Source: SOEP (wave 2009), own calculations.

Note: In total we have 5311 observations, 787 for WFH and 4524 for WIO.

Comparison of Working from Home (WFH) and Working in the Office (WIO)

In addition to inducing higher work effort, employers can benefit from the implementation of working from home, as they can save operating costs due to reduced office space. Though, they should be aware of challenges and potential problems. First, working from home should be an option. As employees have different preferences, mandatory working from home could induce dissatisfaction. Additionally, working from home is experienced by employees as a benefit and a symbol of appreciation and trust if it is

voluntary. Only under this condition, employees respond to working from home with “extra” work effort. Second, a potential drawback of working from home is that it can cause personal and professional isolation, because employees have reduced social interaction .

CONCLUSION

Based on ABCD analysis for the business model “working from home” various factors affecting the issues of the model along with their constituent critical elements are identified and analyst. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compare to constraints and disadvantages of this model, so that working from home model may become more popular from the prospective of employers and employees in the organization in the future.

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